

High-Fidelity Digital Twin Autoclave Tool for Quality Informed Composite Fabrication

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Acknowledgement

This work is funded by Naval Air Warfare Center (NAVAIR), Aircraft Division under the Contract of N68335-23-C-0116.

Motivation

- ❑ Autoclave time is the bottleneck in manufacturing lines increasing overall production time and cost
- ❑ Optimization of the autoclave process by simultaneously curing multiple parts without deviating from the recommended cure cycle can significantly reduce scrap rate and also the overall production time and cost
- ❑ GEM and the team propose to deliver a high-fidelity multi-physics predictive simulation toolkit (SMARTCLAVE) that can optimize the autoclave process condition to balance the throughput and quality of cured-composite parts

Overview of Technical Approach

- Resin curing and kinetics
- Exothermic process and heat generation
- Local turbulence and parts interaction
- Pressurization of composite during processing

- Evolution of degree of cure (DOC)
- Temperature and DOC dependent property evolution
- Thermal-mechanical response of a multi-part system
- Distortion, residual stress, and defects after demolding
- Process optimization (schedule, quality, and throughput)
- Autoclave Consolidation & defect formation model

Summary of SMARTCLAVE Capability

GEM's SMARTCLAVE GUI

Step 1: Autoclave setup

User Inputs:

- CAD model
- Autoclave Parts (i.e., bagging assembly & table)
- Material system
- Part placement

3D interactive interface
(load CAD & adjust placement)

Step 2: Heat Transfer Coefficient

User Inputs:

- Model file with Mesh & BCs
- Time step

Outputs:

- Flow Field
- HTC Field

Step 3: Temperature, Consolidation & Residual stress

User Inputs:

- Model file with Mesh, layup & BCs
- Time step

Outputs:

- Temperature
- Degree of Cure
- Residual stress & Distortion
- Consolidation (thickness change + fiber volume fraction)
- Fabrication induced defects such as ply-waviness, voids & delamination zone

Residual Stress & Distortion

NIAR's Autoclave Experiment on an L-beam

L-Beam Fabrication

Material: IM7/8552
Layup: [45/0/-45/90]3s
Tool: Al 6061 (Convex)

Autoclave Setup

Air temperature measurements close to autoclave back wall.

Air temperature measurements behind part assembly

L-Beam Part & Tool Assembly

- PTC: 19,20,22,23,24
- PTC: 13,14,15,16,17,18
- PTC: 3,4,7,8,11,12
- PTC: 1,2,5,6,9,10
- PTC: 21,25

Temperature [°F] / Pressure [psf] vs Time [minutes]

Temperature [°F] (Left Y-axis, 0 to 375)
Pressure [psf] (Left Y-axis, 0 to 35)
Time [minutes] (X-axis, 0 to 500)
Vacuum [inHg] (Right Y-axis, -35 to 35)

Legend:

- PTC1 - PTC14
- PTC15 - PTC24
- PTC25 - PTC31
- PTC32
- AIRC
- TSET_PART
- PRESS
- SVAC

Thermal Survey Data

Thermal CFD Model

~1.4 million cells

surface refinement
 wake region refinement

Temperature contours with velocity streamlines

Front Section

Rear Section

Q-criterion

User-Defined Multilayer Abaqus Model

Boundary Conditions

Heat Transfer Analysis

- Note:**
- Air temp. follow Cure cycle
 - Spatially Varying HTC from CFD

Stress Analysis Model

Bagging

$$K_{eff} = \frac{K_b K_{air}}{K_b + K_{air}}$$

assumed as a thermal circuit in a series connection

$$K_b = 0.43 \text{ W/m/K}$$

$$K_{air} = 0.015 \text{ W/m/K}$$

$$K_{eff} = 0.0117 \text{ W/m/K}$$

Validation of the Thermal History

Temperature

9in X 10in composite part
Material: IM7/8552
Layup: [45/0/-45/90]3s; 24 plies
Tool: Al 6061 (Convex); 0.25" corner radius

Residual Stress and Distortion Validation

During Cure
(at t=20,548s)

After fully Cured

After Demold

Experiment

Simulation

Von Mises Stress

Unit is Pa

Tool-Part separation

Component 33 of Strain

Front

Rear

Distortion after demolding

Spring-in Deformation

Unit is meter

Conclusions

- Developed a multiphysics CFD modeling approach to capture flow, temperature, and multiple parts interaction in an autoclave
- Developed the customized Abaqus model for thermo-chemo-mechanical prediction using local CFD-driven boundary condition
- Efficient generation of HTC field from CFD results without using exhaustive calibration autoclave runs
- Validated the performance prediction using the measured spring-in angles
- Established a digital twin autoclave for the rational selection of the processing parameters to balance the parts load out and the quality